

SURGICAL TEXTBOOK OUTCOMES IN PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH CHONDROSARCOMA

Abstract ID:

2169132

1. [Anna M. Czarnecka, MD PhD \(she/her/hers\)](#) (Role: Author)
2. [Piotr Remiszewski](#) (Role: Co-Author)
3. [Piotr Blonski \(he/him/his\)](#) (Role: Co-Author)
4. [Agnieszka Zając, PhD](#) (Role: Co-Author)
5. [Bartłomiej Szostakowski, MD PhD \(he/him/his\)](#) (Role: Co-Author)
6. [Andrzej Pienkowski, MD PhD \(he/him/his\)](#) (Role: Co-Author)
7. [Michał Wagrodzki, MD, PhD](#) (Role: Co-Author)
8. [Paweł Teterycz, MD PhD](#) (Role: Co-Author)
9. [Piotr Rutkowski, MD, PhD \(he/him/his\)](#) (Role: Co-Author)

Objective

To characterise clinicopathological features, surgical treatment patterns, and survival outcomes in patients(pts) diagnosed with chondrosarcoma(ChS), and to determine complications following primary ChS resection.

Methods

We retrospectively analysed ChS pts treated at reference centre over the last 25 years. Median relapse-free survival (mRFS) and median overall survival (mOS) were analysed. We used the Kaplan-Meier to calculate the median values of relapse-free survival (mRFS) and overall survival (mOS); the log-rank test was used to assess potential prognostic factors; and Clavien-Dindo scale - to classify surgical complications.

Results

205 ChS pts were included (median age: 51.84 years; 114 male (55.6%), 91 female (44.4%)). Histological subtypes included: conventional (CChS; n=134, 65.4%), secondary peripheral (SChS; n=25, 12.2%), dedifferentiated (DDChS; n=21, 10.2%), mesenchymal (MCS; n=12, 5.9%). The histologic grades were: G1 (n=83, 40.5%), G2 (n=65, 31.7%), G3 (n=38, 18.5%) and Gx (n=13, 6.3%). R0 resection was achieved in 132 pts (64.4%), R1 in 45 pts (22%) and R2 in 19 pts (9.3%). Amputation was performed in 22 cases (10.7%) - mostly due to primary tumour volume (21/22). 110 pts (53.7%) underwent resection with reconstruction, while endoprosthesis was used in 57 pts (27.8%) and curettage in 13 pts (6.3%). Hemipelvectomy was performed in 37 pts (18%) and the Tikhoff-Lindberg procedure in 38 pts (18.5%). The entire cohort demonstrated mRFS of 41.8 months(mo; 5-year: 45.2%), and mOS of 103.6 mo (5-year: 65.2%). Both values were significantly associated with histological grade (log-rank $p < 0.001$), with G3 and Gx subtypes demonstrating markedly poorer outcomes. No surgical complications were observed in 84 pts (41%), Grade II occurred in 58 pts (28.3%), IIIB in 27 pts (13.2%), and I in 26 pts (12.7%). A single grade V fatal event (n=1; 0.5%) was recorded.

Conclusion

ChS represents a high heterogeneity. Histopathological diagnosis, including grade significantly influences patients outcomes. Surgical complications have to be considered in clinical decision-making. These data reinforce the importance of referral to high-volume sarcoma centres capable of achieving wide margins and complex reconstructions.